

SWOT ANALYSIS AND PROPOSALS TO IMPROVE THE DEVELOPMENT FOR TRAINING YOUNG TAEKWONDO ATHLETES IN VIETNAM

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Abstract:

Based on a research of the theory to practice in training, coaching the young athletes generation and in particular Taekwondo, we have carried out a SWOT analysis (Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Challenge) in the training young athletes of Vietnam Taekwondo in the current period, and outlined a number of measures appropriate solutions to contribute to development in the right direction for the training young athletes to meet recruitment goals and competition of the higher levels (national team).

Keywords: training young athletes; Taekwondo development solutions

1. Introduction

Together with the development of the country in exchanging information and integrating with other countries in the world in all aspects such as economy, politics, social culture, education etc., sports in general as well as martial arts Taekwondo in particular have made significant breakthroughs. Young athlete training can be considered as a long-term strategic goal in the development of high achievement sports. According to Vu Xuan Thanh, Head of Taekwondo Department, Department of Sport of Vietnam said: "*The training of young athletes is a long-term investment plan for the big arena.*" In addition, the development of Taekwondo career must meets the requirements of expanding relations with countries in the world, raise the position of the Vietnamese sports in the international arena, and meet the expectations of those who are interested in this martial art. The achievements of Taekwondo in regional, continental and world competitions have contributed to enhancing the performance of Vietnamese sports in the international arena, and promoting Taekwondo Vietnam to reach the international qualification standards to attend the Olympics.

Table 1: Vietnamese Taekwondo performance in the recent SEA Games

Year	The times of organizing	Host countries	Name of competition	Gold medals
2003	22	Vietnam	SEA Games	5
2005	23	Philippines	SEA Games	5
2007	24	Thailand	SEA Games	4
2009	25	Laos	SEA Games	5
2011	26	Indonesia	SEA Games	3
2013	27	Myanmar	SEA Games	5
2015	28	Singapore	SEA Games	5
2017	29	Malaysia	SEA Games	4

In 1994, the first time, athlete Tran Quang Ha won a gold medal in the Asian Taekwondo held in Hiroshima, Japan. Four years later in Bangkok, Thailand, Taekwondo Vietnam got another gold medal by Ho Nhat Thong. And at the 2000 Olympic Games held in Sydney - Australia, Vietnam's athletics first achieved a silver medal with the outstanding performance of female athlete Taekwondo Tran Hieu Ngan. This is an important milestone for Taekwondo Vietnam on the world stage. But this achievement is not maintained in the following Olympic Games. And so far, no Taekwondo athlete has ever won gold medals at the Asian Games or the Olympics. Even worse, at the 2016 Olympics, for the first time Vietnam Taekwondo athletes did not qualify for the Olympics, because all Vietnamese Taekwondo athletes failed in the first round.

According to Truong Ngoc De, President of the Vietnam Taekwondo Federation, "Every year, we select players through four tournaments: regional tournaments, youth tournaments, national championships and championships for clubs to find out good athletes. At present, the Federation has divided into areas with experts to supervise directly, and find out the young talent to have good athletes later (after training). So, the question is why Vietnam Taekwondo is not growing, even it can be said that Vietnam Taekwondo lagged behind the region and the world.

In the countries with good sport result such as the United States, China, South Korea etc., the training of young athletes (competitors for future) is considered as one of the urgent and essential issues. Focusing on key issues such as: selection, training of athletes; management and education of athletes; and applying science in selection and training. Besides, there is also the need for the support from national policies.

In Vietnam, the governing party and state have also paid attention to the development of good performance in sports. Directive 36 / TW of Vietnam stated: "Mục tiêu trước trước mắt là huấn luyện, đào tạo được những vận động viên trẻ có thành tích tốt..." (The immediate objective is to train and have practice schedule for young athletes with good achievements ...). But now the training is not suitable in the actual situation. Sports centers, provinces, cities where different implementation, training model is not united. For example, in some places, intensive training is applying (athletes must stay in the training places until weekend); in some places athletes are free. They come to the training places and they get home after they finish training, they are not managed by any organization); the selection of athletes varies from place to

place; Regimes of fostering, learning general knowledge and others facilities of young athletes are not the same.

Therefore, it is difficult to find a relatively perfect model for the training of young athletes in Vietnam today. So, we have studied, researched, and interviewed the coaches, experts, sports managers together with the state supporting policies in the sport development. This will be used as a basis for SWOT analyzes for the training of young athletes, checking qualified young athletes for domestic taekwondo competition and proposing appropriate solutions for development.

In this study, we used the following methods: referencing book method; investigation method, expert interview method and statistical methods.

Research subjects are: management and training policies, management model of training and competition and policies related to the training of young Vietnamese Taekwondo athletes in the current period.

2. Results of Research

2.1. Introduction to SWOT analysis

For a long time, SWOT analysis has been used extensively in various fields and has been used by a number of experts such as Ansoff (1965) in the company's development strategy. The author analyses the development of the company, and makes strategic planning. Hofer and Schendel (1978) have analyzed and pointed out the impacts on sports and physical activity such as the analysis of work environment, human resources, and weaknesses that need to overcome. And then, the author assesses and decides the feasible strategy and creates a development advantage. [1]

SWOT analysis is a research of: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of the subject of study. SWOT analysis is a strategic approach to assess and identify the subjects and resources of analysis through comprehensive internal, external influences to take corrective measurement to ensure the most practical plan, to make the current performance get the best achievement. SWOT analysis is based on the following three characteristics: system analysis, previous data, current and future data; validation, directional selection and potential development impacts.

In this study, we focused on the SWOT analysis of young Taekwondo athlete training in Vietnam, identifying strengths and weaknesses as well as external opportunities and challenges that affect the result to enhance high performance for sports in our homeland.

2.2. Content of SWOT analysis on the training of young Vietnamese Taekwondo athletes

Based on the survey results, we conducted a SWOT analysis to clarify the issues relating to the training of young Taekwondo athletes. From this base, we will have orientations and strategies to develop, and minimize the potential risks that affect the long-term development of sports in Vietnam in general as well as Taekwondo in particular.

2.2.1. Strengths

Including the factors promoting the sport development of the country, the advantages derived from the policies, the development orientation of the sport as well as the development policies of the state. For example, in Resolution No. 08-NQ / TW, *"investment in physical education and sport is an investment in human resources for the development of the country. Increasing in physical training and sport facilities and training high-achievement athletes and at the same time bringing into full play the social resources for the development of physical training and sports. On physical training and sports, the government should strongly promote the role of social organizations in the management and administration of physical training and sport activities ..."* ("Đầu tư cho thể dục, thể thao là đầu tư cho con người, cho sự phát triển của đất nước. Tăng tỷ lệ chi ngân sách nhà nước, ưu tiên đầu tư xây dựng cơ sở vật chất thể dục, thể thao và đào tạo vận động viên thể thao thành tích cao; đồng thời phát huy các nguồn lực của xã hội để phát triển thể dục, thể thao. Đổi mới quản lý nhà nước về thể dục, thể thao, phát huy mạnh mẽ vai trò của các tổ chức xã hội trong quản lý, điều hành các hoạt động thể dục, thể thao...") [2].

And Resolution 16/2013 / NQ-CP also directed: *"Develop a plan for the development of athletes of key sports; to expand and modernize the national sport training centers, to actively prepare the necessary facilities to be ready for the 18th Asian Games in 2019. Completing high performance sports and sports systems to promote industries and localities to develop and improve the performance of key sports"* ("Xây dựng kế hoạch phát triển lực lượng vận động viên các môn thể thao trọng điểm; mở rộng quy mô và hiện đại hóa các trung tâm huấn luyện thể thao quốc gia, tích cực chuẩn bị cơ sở vật chất, kỹ thuật cần thiết để sẵn sàng tổ chức Đại hội thể thao châu Á lần thứ 18 năm 2019. Hoàn thiện hệ thống thi đấu thể thao thành tích cao, thể thao chuyên nghiệp nhằm thúc đẩy các ngành, các địa phương phát triển và nâng cao thành tích các môn thể thao trọng điểm") [3].

The policies of the state in general as well as the developing plan of the Taekwondo League in particular have created the most favorable conditions for Taekwondo development. In addition, the promotion and development of mass sports and school sports is well respected because this is a huge human resource to recruit athletes for the national team. *"To intensify investment in the construction of physical training and sport infrastructure, such as centers, multi-purpose training areas, training and playgrounds with simple equipment in districts wards, communes, residential areas etc. to create a network of physical training and sport facilities to meet the daily training needs of the people; To build pilot models of multi-purpose houses serving cultural and sports workers in the provinces and centrally-run cities where exist industrial zones."* ("Tăng cường đầu tư xây dựng cơ sở hạ tầng thể dục, thể thao công cộng, như: Các trung tâm, khu tập luyện đa năng, các điểm tập luyện, vui chơi với các trang thiết bị đơn giản tại các quận, huyện, phường, xã, khu dân cư... tạo mạng lưới hạ tầng thể dục, thể thao đáp ứng nhu cầu tập luyện hàng ngày của nhân dân; xây dựng mô hình thí điểm nhà đa năng phục vụ văn hóa, thể thao công nhân ở các tỉnh, thành phố trực thuộc Trung ương có khu công nghiệp") and *"To well perform physical education under the curriculum and strongly develop extra-curricular sports activities of pupils and students; continue to develop sports gifted schools to discover and train national athletic talents*

” (*“Thực hiện tốt giáo dục thể chất theo chương trình nội khóa và phát triển mạnh các hoạt động thể thao ngoại khóa của học sinh, sinh viên; tiếp tục phát triển các trường lớp năng khiếu thể thao để phát hiện, đào tạo tài năng thể thao quốc gia”*) [3]

Table 2: Strengths analysis

Content	Form	Result
Governing party, state and sport sectors have policies to support and develop physical training and sports.	Decrees and circulars of the governing party and the state	State-run sport and physical training activities
Most people, including students participate in Taekwondo activities	Families, social organizations, businessmen	Achievements are important factors for development
Authorities regularly organize tournaments	The close guidance of Party leaders as well as the sport sectors.	highly effective sport activities in selection and evaluation

2.2.2. Weaknesses

Weaknesses are disadvantages from factors such as lacking suitable planning and selection methods, because each local authority has different selecting methods; the authorities do not apply effectively scientific factors to the selection; the funding for recruitment and training is limited; qualifications and competence of trainers are limited; The policies for athletes are not suitable, so it has not attracted sports talents; and low economic conditions also make many athletes leave the profession.

In Article 1 of Decision No. 234/2006 / QD-TTg the requirements for the payment in Vietnam dong (Vietnam currency) by day to Vietnamese coaches and athletes during the training and competition period are as followed.

A. For Coach:

- The head coach of the national youth team: 100,000 VND / person / day (about 4.7 US dollar/ person / day); (1 US dollar is equivalent to 22,600 Vietnam dong)
- Coaches for National youth team: VND 75,000 / person / day (about 3.5 US dollar/ person / day);
- Coaches for youth team of the localities, provinces and big cities directly under control of the Government: 55,000 VND / person / day (about 2.5 US dollar/ person / day);
- Trainers of talented teams of the localities, provinces and big cities directly under control of the Government: 55,000 VND / person / day (about 2.5 US dollar/ person / day);

B. For athlete

- Athlete of Youth team of the localities, provinces and big cities directly under control of the Government: 25,000 VND / person / day (about 1.1 US dollar/ person / day);
- The athlete of talented team of the provinces, cities directly under the control of the government: 15,000 VND / person / day (about 0.6 US dollar/ person / day); [4].

Due to the above reasons, difficulties and obstacles in the selection and training of athletes in our country do not fully assess the athlete's capacity, the coaches do not dedicate to the profession and there are some families not wanting their children to participate in the sport teams. So if we, the planners, policy makers, training-model builders solve these disadvantages, the problem can be overcome easily.

Table 3: Weakness analysis

Content	Reason	Consequence
No inheriting forces	Due to policies and funding	Having disadvantages and not developing high sport achievement
The performance in competition is poor	The concept and method of training is outdated	The content of training is not up-to-date applied
Marketization, and socialization of Taekwondo is not high enough	Economic life, and social awareness is low	Taekwondo development has many disadvantages

2.2.3. Opportunities

Opportunity is the external environment contributing to the development of Taekwondo; utilizing, and grasping the opportunities to create the highest advantages. In the selection and training Taekwondo to young athletes, the opportunities are from the supporting policies from state, access to advanced scientific training methods, and the invitation of foreign experts to train coaches, activating mass sport movement throughout the country. At the same time, Taekwondo training schools such as Ho Chi Minh City University of Physical Education and Sports, Da Nang University of Sports and Physical Training, Tu Son Sports University, Bac Ninh Sports University etc. should be the professional Taekwondo training centers. These centers are the places to create well-trained, well-educated, knowledgeable, dynamic and creative trainers. If we have good opportunities, polices, and solidarity for a unique goal, I believe that we will have a good successive force for the world competition and get the medals for the country.

Table 4: Opportunity analysis

Content	Reason	Result
Establishing goals and strategies for developing high-achievement sports	An indispensable requirement of the national sport development goals	To meet the goal of getting high achievements in international competitions
Gradual changing and raising awareness of mass sports	The standard of living of trainers and athletes develops gradually, and their spiritual lives advanced	A good opportunity for development
Improving and paying more attention to the life and spirit of athletes	The role of sport and physical training authorities and state	Playing an important role in the development of physical training and sports.
Regularly participating in domestic and international tournaments.	Show national status in the international arena.	Much attention is paid to sport development.

2.2.4. Challenges

These are the adverse externalities that threaten the development of domestic sports and the possible risks such as: the impact from the well-developed sport countries like Thailand, South Korea, China and etc. There are many different sports for children to choose from, and the support is also the great challenge for trained athletes. Moreover, the time for learning general knowledge at high school also affects the training and competition process. Or the family does not support the children to participate in the teams for fear of affecting the results of learning at high school.

Table 5: Analysis of challenges

Content	Reason	Result
The level of competition of athletes in the world is very high.	Scientific technology, and economic development of many countries are at high level	Relying on the actual situation of countries around the world
Rapid industrialization and modernization	Focusing mainly on knowledge at high school, not focusing on sport	Do not choose sport and physical training as a career
There are so many sports to come out rapidly	Uneven development strategies	Obstruct the development of high athletic performance

Thus, identifying the strengths and weaknesses is the internal factors, and the opportunities and challenges are external factors. SWOT analysis is to set the development goals for the authorities to find out the core problem to solve and find the countermeasures for it.

2.3. Solutions to develop the training of young Taekwondo athletes.

In the research, when we interview experts and managers, we propose some solutions as follows:

Firstly, the selection of athletes:

By applying of scientific methods into the selection, selecting athletes through various forms such as: through the tournament, through the examination of the athlete's performance, through the observation of training, through the centers and by good recruiting and training, we will evaluate accurately the athlete so that we could select the suitable ones for the competitions

Secondly, management:

Sport management plays an important role in the development of sports and physical training (management of daily activities, study, leisure and eating of athletes). Not only managing the athlete but also managing the coach tightly is very necessary. From the management we will be able to detect and solve problems that may occur with athletes and coaches. If the management is done well, the efficiency of athlete training will be improved.

Thirdly, constantly improving the level of learning and coaching for athletes and coaches respectively:

In practice, the training of coaches and athletes is not reasonable: a coach who is negative in training, lacking dynamic, lazy at work; having bad professional qualifications, computer skills, foreign languages will have difficulties in accessing to advanced science. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance both professional and general skills. By regularly organizing training courses, and competing with countries with excellent athletes in Korea, China, Thailand and etc. will improve the level of the athlete. Knowledgeable athletes will be able to acquire skills and knowledge better and have good tactics in thinking and in competition.

Fourthly, applying science in training:

Applying science in athlete training will be the key to improve the technical-tactical level. We need to focus on researching and finding the best solutions for Taekwondo development. Throughout the study, we will find out what make the development of Taekwondo, as well as explain the proper operation and training methods of Taekwondo. Today, science and technology are developing rapidly, so managers and coaches must be able to apply science into their training, besides their own experience.

Fifthly, funding:

There should be a reasonable regime for practicing and training payment. If payments do not meet the basic needs of the coaches and athletes, there will be bad effect to the spirit of training. There should be funding for the team to regularly training, and practicing. To have funds we should call for individuals and social organizations to donate to sport and physical training, get more funding from outside for training and practicing activities, and broadcast and publicize the activities so that we could have a generation of quality athletes.

Sixthly, focusing on training the successors:

Training young athletes is a very necessary and urgent task. If we do not pay attention to this, then at some time the development of high performance for Taekwondo will come to an end. Therefore, it is necessary to have a plan for training, promoting training from sport movements for public, from sport schools, etc. and to draw up plans for the organization of annual tournaments at all levels. Through these activities, a large number of athletes are involved, whereby we select talented athletes as the core of the teams. We should facilitate the most for both and trainers and athletes with incentive systems, and minimize the factors that cause difficulties for young athletes in training and competition.

Seventhly, Educate athletes:

Teaching general knowledge and moral lessons are very significant in the process of psychological formation. The strong will and confidence of athletes are important in forming their love to the country, their aim in life, and their courage and devotion for their country. Because, today, with the rapid change of society, and the developed economy, young athletes should be educated the political thought to direct them to do the right things.

Eighthly, about policy:

There should be suitable incentives for both coaches and athletes so that they can focus in their practice and training. Besides, having suitable reward policies for individuals and teams that have contributed to the physical training and sport movement is a must. There should be supporting for difficult situations. And creating suitable jobs for athletes when they are too old to compete is necessary.

3. Conclusion

The results of the analysis have clearly identified factors that may limit the development of sport and physical training in general as well as Taekwondo in particular. Based on these limitations and challenges we can overcome and make them advantages. And the solutions that we consulted from the experts as well as the result of the research will be a good solution in this period. We are sure that if these solutions are applied and implemented thoroughly and comprehensively, we will certainly succeed.

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